

THE DIAGNOSTIC VALUE OF ULTRASOUND ARTIFACTS IN THE MANAGEMENT OF COVID-19 PNEUMONIA

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Abstract

Abstract: Lung ultrasonography (LUS) has emerged as a non-invasive, rapid, and reliable diagnostic modality for COVID-19 pneumonia. By analyzing pleural artifacts, including horizontal A-lines and vertical B-lines, LUS allows detection of interstitial syndromes, consolidations, and pleural irregularities. In this study, 50 hospitalized patients with confirmed or suspected COVID-19 were examined using standardized BLUE and CLUE protocols across 3, 6, and 12 lung zones, with comparative analysis to computed tomography (CT). Findings demonstrate that LUS provides accurate bedside assessment, detects early pathological changes, monitors disease progression, and differentiates viral from bacterial pneumonia. LUS is particularly valuable in emergency, ward, and intensive care settings, offering a cost-effective, radiation-free, repeatable alternative to CT.

Keywords: Lung ultrasonography, COVID-19, B-lines, A-lines, BLUE protocol, CLUE protocol, interstitial pneumonia, critical care.

Ultrasound examination of the organ with the largest volume in the human body—the lung—had long been considered uninformative. A normally aerated healthy lung represents a major acoustic barrier to ultrasound. However, deeper investigation into the subject has revealed not only the feasibility of sonography but also its real and potential benefits in the diagnosis and management of emergency cases presenting with dyspnea [1–3].

The pioneer of lung ultrasonography is considered to be the intensivist and anesthesiologist Professor Daniel Lichtenstein from the Ambroise-Paré University Hospital in Paris, who in 1991 developed the method of so-called “critical ultrasound”—a comprehensive approach to ultrasound examination in emergency and critical care settings, including thoracic organs and lungs, alongside transthoracic echocardiography [2,3].

The analysis of this examination is based on artifacts originating from the pleura. Since most acute respiratory disorders involve the pleura, this structure is accessible to ultrasound. The hyperechogenic pleural line consists of the parietal and visceral pleura with the potential space between them. Normally, it moves synchronously with the respiratory cycle—a phenomenon known as lung sliding. The absence of lung sliding indicates pneumothorax with 100% specificity [1,4,5].

Lung ultrasonography identifies several sonographic signs, some of which are characteristic of normally aerated lungs, while specific combinations of these signs may indicate pathological processes. The semiology of lung ultrasound includes artifacts generated at air–tissue interfaces [1,4,5]. These artifacts are classified as horizontal (A-lines) and vertical (B-lines).

A-lines are horizontal reverberation artifacts appearing at equal distances from each other, corresponding to the thickness of the soft tissues between the skin and pleura. They can be seen both in normal lungs and in various pathologic conditions, depending on the combination of findings [1,4].

B-lines are vertical artifacts that arise from the pleural line and extend to the bottom of the screen without fading. They are observed in both normal lungs and in lungs with various degrees of deaeration. The presence of three or more B-lines between two ribs is referred to as “lung rockets” and correlates with interstitial syndrome, showing a 93% sensitivity for alveolar–interstitial radiographic changes and complete concordance with findings on computed tomography. When fewer than three B-lines are visible (“septal rockets”), this corresponds to Kerley B-lines on chest radiography and indicates thickened interlobular septa seen in interstitial syndrome [5,6].

Several protocols have been developed for lung ultrasonography, each designed for specific clinical purposes. For the differential diagnosis of diseases causing acute dyspnea, the BLUE protocol (Bedside Lung Ultrasonography in Emergency) is widely applied. In addition, based primarily on echographic assessment of the lungs, the FALLS protocol (Fluid Administration Limited by Lung Sonography) serves as a valuable tool for determining therapeutic strategies in cases of shock of unknown etiology [7].

According to these protocols, examination of the patient is performed using three-point scanning for each hemithorax: the right and left anterior upper BLUE points, the anterior lower BLUE points, and the posterolateral alveolar and/or pleural syndrome (PLAPS) points on both sides.

Three standardized points are identified:

1. Upper BLUE point – located in the middle of the upper hand.
2. Lower BLUE point – located in the middle of the lower hand.
3. PLAPS point – defined as the intersection of a horizontal line drawn at the level of the lower BLUE point and the vertical posterior axillary line [7].

The use of small-footprint probes allows positioning as posteriorly as possible in supine patients, thereby enhancing the sensitivity for detecting posterolateral al-

veolar and/or pleural syndromes (PLAPS). The diaphragm is typically located at the lower margin of the lower hand [20].

Using the BLUE protocol, it is possible to accurately diagnose a wide range of pulmonary pathologies, including pneumothorax (with diagnostic accuracy comparable to computed tomography and higher specificity than chest radiography), pleural effusion, pulmonary edema, interstitial syndrome, pneumonia, atelectasis, pulmonary embolism, and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) [9,10].

Lung ultrasonography can play a significant role during the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. Based on lung ultrasound findings and clinical data from the Molinette MedUrg Group on Lung Ultrasound, in cases with false-negative results during early PCR testing, diagnosis can be established with an accuracy of up to 94.4% [11,12].

During the progression of COVID-19, parenchymal changes in the lungs typically begin in the distal regions and progressively extend proximally. In the early phase, computed tomography (CT) often demonstrates a “ground-glass” pattern and a “crazy paving” appearance, whereas in later stages, larger consolidations are observed, primarily in the basal or dependent lung regions. The most frequently affected regions are

the right middle and lower lobes, followed by the left upper lobe.

Histopathologically, COVID-19 pneumonia progresses in the distal lung regions and is characterized by alveolar damage and edema, interstitial thickening, and gravity-dependent consolidations. Consequently, the pathological progression of COVID-19 pneumonia is well suited for surface visualization techniques, such as lung ultrasonography [8].

The clinical presentation of COVID-19 is highly variable, ranging from asymptomatic infection to severe, life-threatening pneumonia with major complications. Severe disease typically develops approximately one week after symptom onset, characterized by rapidly progressing respiratory failure and acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS)—bilateral, non-cardiogenic pulmonary edema caused by fluid overload, leading to severe hypoxemia.

Although the pathophysiology of lung injury in COVID-19 meets the Berlin criteria for ARDS, COVID-19 pneumonia is described as exhibiting two phenotypes: “non-ARDS” (Type I) and “ARDS” (Type II). Among imaging modalities, computed tomography (CT) of the lungs remains the gold standard. Therefore, the efficacy and utility of other imaging techniques, including ultrasonography, are primarily assessed in comparison with CT findings [13,14]. (Table 1).

Table 1.

Characteristics of COVID-19 pneumonia on computed tomography (CT) and lung ultrasonography. Adapted from Peng QY, Wang XT, Zhang LN. Findings of lung ultrasonography of novel coronavirus pneumonia during the 2019–2020 epidemic. *Intensive Care Med.* 2020;46(5):849–850. [21].

Lung CT	LUS
Thickened pleura	Thickened pleural line
Ground glass opacity	B-lines(multifocal,discrete,or confluent)
Infiltrating shadows	Confluent B-lines
Sub-pleural consolidation	Small consolidations
Translobar consolidation	Non-translobar+translobar consolidations
Rare pleural effusions	Rare pleural effusions
More than two pulmonary lobes affected	Conspicuous features distributed on a multilobar basis

Since COVID-19 pneumonia most frequently exhibits peripheral, superficial involvement, predominantly affecting the lower lobes, the pathological changes are accessible to lung ultrasonography (with a penetration depth of 14–16 cm). Lung ultrasound is particularly advantageous in the emergency department during the pandemic due to its availability, high diagnostic accuracy for pulmonary diseases, and low cost.

Lung ultrasonography can be performed using linear, curved (abdominal), or sector (cardiac) probes. During the examination, the probe is positioned parallel or perpendicular to the intercostal spaces. Recommended imaging depth is 8–10 cm (6–8 cm in asthenic individuals, 10–12 cm in hypersthenic individuals).

The examination is performed sequentially, starting from the most frequently affected regions toward the less affected areas: from the dorsal surfaces, progressing caudally to cranially, then moving to lateral, and finally anterior surfaces. Each region is observed over approximately one respiratory cycle (5–6 seconds). The number of artifacts is recorded per intercostal space.

The Lichtenstein nomenclature using the so-called Volpicelli zones is applied [15,16,17,18], with six regions per hemithorax. Each region is evaluated using a three-point scoring system.

The lung ultrasound score (LUS) is a semi-quantitative model that considers 12 regions and the presence of specific artifacts resulting from extravascular fluid accumulation and/or loss of aeration. The total score ranges from 0 to a theoretical maximum of 36 points (consolidation in all regions). [22].

For the ultrasound assessment of patients, the CLUE protocol was developed by Australian intensivists and trainees, enabling the triage of COVID-19 patients based on a lung ultrasound scoring system [19].

Based on the existing knowledge of lung ultrasound and the experience gained in European countries, from December 2020 we decided to implement lung ultrasound for patients in the therapeutic ward. Each patient was evaluated within the clinical context, incorporating laboratory and instrumental findings as well as objective clinical data, with particular emphasis on the analysis of computed tomography (CT) results.

Ultrasound examinations were performed according to both established lung ultrasound protocols (BLUE and CLUE), assessing 3, 6, and 8 zones per lung, with patients examined in both supine and seated positions. Notably, the 12-zone assessment, as outlined in the CLUE protocol, was considered the most optimal approach for evaluating COVID-19 patients.

During the process of practically applying the fundamental principles of lung ultrasound, approximately 50 patients were examined dynamically to ensure that the results could be interpreted reliably both technically and clinically. In total, up to 90 examinations were conducted across the following groups (laboratory-confirmed COVID-19):

1. Patients with prolonged fever
2. Patients on the first day of hospitalization
3. Patients presenting with clinical manifestations of COVID-19 but negative PCR results
4. Pregnant patients

5. Patients with community-acquired pneumonia (PCR-negative)

The following section presents selected ultrasound findings from these examinations.

Patient N1: Male, 61 years old (Figure 1). The patient was admitted to the clinic on March 5, 2021. On the same day, lung ultrasound (LUS) examination revealed consolidations in zones R6 and R4 on the right lung, while B-lines were observed in all other zones bilaterally, except in R1, L1, and L2, with more than three B-lines per intercostal space and occupying >50% of the examined area. The total ultrasound score was 11–12 points.

Chest CT of the same patient demonstrated bilateral, patchy, small- to medium-sized ground-glass opacities, predominantly in the basal regions, with small consolidative foci. Semi-quantitative analysis of CT images yielded a lung involvement index of 12 points (scale 0–24) (Table 2).

Comparative Analysis: LUS vs CT

Parameter	Lung Ultrasound (LUS)	Computed Tomography (CT)
Extent of involvement	11–12 points – diffuse B-lines and consolidations	12 points – ground-glass opacities + consolidations
Localization	R6, R4 – consolidation; B-lines bilaterally	All lung fields bilaterally, predominantly basal
Detail	Consolidation and interstitial pattern	Precise localization, type, and volume of lesions
Advantages	Rapid, bedside, radiation-free	High accuracy and detailed visualization
Limitations	Incomplete visualization of deep zones	Radiation exposure, high cost, difficult transport

Conclusion:

Both methods (LUS and CT) provided consistent and reliable information regarding interstitial and alveolar involvement characteristic of COVID-19 pneumonia.

Lung ultrasound demonstrated a good correlation with CT findings, particularly in terms of B-line distribution and consolidations.

Accordingly, LUS can be considered an effective and rapid alternative for assessment of severely ill or urgent patients; however, final diagnosis and precise volumetric assessment of pulmonary involvement remain dependent on CT imaging.

Patient N1: Male, 61 years old (Figure 1).

Table 2.

Lung ultrasound by zone in Patient N1

Zone	B-lines / Thickened pleural line	Subpleural consolidation	Large consolidation / Air bronchogram
R1	-	-	-
R2	+	-	-
R3	+	-	-
R4	-	+	-
R5	+	-	-
R6	-	+	-
L1	-	-	-
L2	- / +	-	-
L3	+	-	-
L4	+	-	-
L5	+	-	-
L6	+	-	-
Total	11–12 points	-	-

Patient N2: Female, 55 years old (Figure 2). The patient was admitted on March 12, 2021. Chest CT demonstrated ground-glass opacities with pronounced interstitial thickening. Lung ultrasound (LUS) was performed on March 16, 2021. In all examined regions except L1 and L2, multiple and confluent B-lines (“waterfall sign”) were observed, with associated pleural thickening. The total ultrasound score was 10 points (Table 3).

CT imaging of this patient showed bilateral, peripherally localized, small ground-glass nodular opacities with interstitial thickening across multiple lung fields. Semi-quantitative analysis of the CT data

yielded a lung involvement index of 6 points (scale 0–24).

Due to clinical and laboratory deterioration, the patient was subsequently transferred to the intensive care unit (ICU). A repeat chest CT with semi-quantitative analysis showed an increased lung involvement index of 16 points (scale 0–24).

- The initial CT findings were lower than the LUS score.
- During follow-up, it became apparent that LUS detected more severe early-stage involvement than the initial CT.

Comparative Analysis: LUS vs CT

Parameter	Lung Ultrasound (LUS)	Computed Tomography (CT)
Extent of involvement	10 points – multiple B-lines and waterfall sign	Initially 6 points, subsequently 16 points
Details	Intense interstitial involvement, pleural thickening	Ground-glass nodules, interstitial thickening
Level of detail	Rapid visualization of peripheral lesions	Precise volumetric assessment across all segments
Possible interpretation	Disease already in a progressive phase at the time of LUS	Initial CT may have underestimated disease extent
Limitations / Advantages	Identified progressing lesions – early detection	Radiation exposure, high accuracy, but delayed representation of progression

Conclusion:

In this case, lung ultrasound (LUS) detected significant pathological changes early (10 points), which were not fully visualized on the initial CT scan (6 points). During follow-up, as the patient's clinical sta-

tus worsened, the CT involvement index markedly increased (16 points), confirming the high sensitivity of LUS for early detection of disease progression.

This case highlights the value of LUS as a monitoring and early detection tool, particularly in patients whose clinical condition changes rapidly.

Figure 2

Table 3.

Lung ultrasound findings by zone in Patient N2

Zone	B-lines / Thickened pleural line	Subpleural consolidation	Large consolidation / Air bronchogram
R1	+	-	-
R2	+	-	-
R3	+	-	-
R4	+	-	-
R5	+	-	-
R6	+	-	-
L1	-	-	-
L2	-	-	-
L3	+	-	-
L4	+	-	-
L5	+	-	-
L6	+	-	-
Total	10 points	-	-

Patient N3: Female, 62 years old (Figure 3). The patient was admitted on March 10, 2021. Lung ultrasound (LUS) was performed on March 13, 2021. In the anterior zones and upper lateral point on the left, no pathological changes were observed. The total LUS score was 7–8 points (table4). Chest CT demonstrated typical ground-glass opacities.

CT imaging showed bilateral diffuse reduction in lung transparency, with small, isolated ground-glass opacities in various lung fields. Semi-quantitative analysis of the CT data yielded a lung involvement index of 4 points (scale 0–24).

Comparative Analysis: LUS vs CT

Parameter	Lung Ultrasound (LUS)	Computed Tomography (CT)
Extent of involvement	7–8 points – mostly limited changes	4 points – isolated ground-glass changes
Details	No involvement in anterior left zones; focal B-lines	Diffuse reduction in transparency; discrete lesions
Level of detail	Good sensitivity at zonal level	Precise segmental assessment
Possible interpretation	Adequate correlation with CT in mild cases	Confirms LUS evaluation of minor lesions
Limitations / Advantages	Simple, bedside applicable	Requires patient mobilization; detailed imaging

Conclusion:

In patient N3, both lung ultrasound (7–8 points) and chest CT (4 points) demonstrated mild, focal pulmonary lesions. The results of both modalities were consistent, highlighting the reliability of LUS in diagnosing mild cases. The absence of findings in the left

anterior and upper lateral zones underscores the zonal specificity of LUS.

This case demonstrates that LUS, despite its limitations in deep lung structures, effectively reflects mild disease, especially when CT is unavailable or not immediately feasible.

Figure 3

Lung ultrasound fi by zone in Patient N3

Table 4.

Zone	B-lines / Thickened pleural line	Subpleural consolidation	Large consolidation / Air bronchogram
R1	-	-	-
R2	-	-	-
R3	+	-	-
R4	+	-	-
R5	+	-	-
R6	+	-	-
L1	-	-	-
L2	-	-	-
L3	-	-	-
L4	+	-	-
L5	+	-	-
L6	+	-	-
Total	7–8 points	-	-

Patient N4 – Male, 49 years old (Fig. 4)

The patient was admitted on 08/01, with COVID-19 confirmed since 04/01. CT assessment showed a

lung damage index of 5 points on 08/01, which increased to 22 points on 14/01. Lung ultrasound (LUS) was performed on 20/01 and assessed at 16 points (Table 5).

Comparative analysis: LUS vs CT

Parameter	Lung Ultrasound (LUS)	Computed Tomography (CT)
Extent of involvement	16 points – progressive, widespread lesions	08/01 – 5 points; 14/01 – 22 points
Details	Focal lesions, likely with consolidations and prominent B-lines	Diffuse ground-glass opacities, likely with consolidations
Level of detail	Possible waterfall signs and pleural alterations	Accurate assessment of structural and volumetric damage
Possible interpretation	Acute phase of disease – already progressed	Evolutionary course corresponds to LUS findings (CT performed 6 days earlier)
Limitations / Advantages	Performed during peak phase – confirms high-risk features	Allows dynamic assessment at early and late stages

Conclusion:

In Patient N4, the clinical course demonstrated rapid disease progression, with the CT lung damage index increasing fivefold within six days (5 → 22 points). The LUS performed on 20/01 showed a high score (16

points), corresponding to the acute stage of the disease and effectively confirming the severe damage observed on CT. This case further highlights the high diagnostic value of LUS in acute and dynamically progressive COVID-19 pneumonia.

Figure 4

Table 5.

Lung ultrasound findings by zone in Patient N4			
Zone	B-lines / Thickened pleural line	Subpleural consolidation	Large consolidation / Air bronchogram
R1	+	-	-
R2	+	-	-
R3	+	-	-
R4	-	+	-
R5	-	+	-
R6	-	+	-
L1	-	-	-
L2	-	-	-
L3	+	-	-
L4	-	+	-
L5	+	-	-
L6	+	+	-
Total	16point	-	-

Patient N5, female, 63 years old (Figure 5). The patient presented on 17/03 with symptoms suggestive of COVID-19; however, both rapid antigen and PCR tests were negative. According to the medical history, she had experienced intermittent fever, arthralgia, general weakness, anosmia, and ageusia since early February. She had previously been treated in another facility for presumed pneumonia, without laboratory confirmation of COVID-19. Despite empirical treatment for 4–5 days, fever persisted, prompting hospital admission. Chest X-ray demonstrated bilateral infiltrates.

Lung ultrasound (LUS) was performed on 17/03 and revealed COVID-19-like alterations: irregular,

thickened pleural line and >3 B-lines per intercostal space were observed in R3, R4, R5, R6, L4, L5, and L6 zones.

Conclusion:

In this case, despite the lack of laboratory confirmation for COVID-19, the combination of clinical symptoms (anosmia, ageusia, fever, fatigue) and imaging features (bilateral infiltrates on X-ray and characteristic LUS findings) strongly suggests the presence of COVID-19-like viral pneumonia. This case underscores the diagnostic value of lung ultrasound even when laboratory confirmation is unavailable or inconclusive.

Figure 5

Patient N6, pregnant, 35 weeks gestation (Figure 6). The patient, 30 years old, was admitted on 25/05 with laboratory-confirmed COVID-19 (diagnosed on 16/05). She presented with persistent low-grade fever and SpO₂ of 95%. Lung ultrasound (LUS) was performed on 25/05 and revealed multiple B-lines in L5, L6, R4, R5, and R6 zones. Thickened, irregular pleural lines were observed in L6, R5, and R6 zones.

In healthy pregnant patients, especially in the third trimester, the physiologically elevated diaphragm due to the enlarged uterus naturally reduces lung excursion and may result in fluid accumulation. This often manifests as B-lines in the posterior-basal zones bilaterally on LUS, which are characteristic of an interstitial pattern. In this patient, the presence of irregular and thick-

ened pleural lines allows differentiation between physiological changes associated with pregnancy and COVID-19–related alterations. (Table 6)

Clinical Interpretation:

- LUS findings are consistent with mild COVID-19–associated interstitial pneumonia.
- Alterations are localized to typical zones (posterior-basal).
- Pathological pleural line changes serve as the main differentiating feature from physiological pregnancy-related changes.

Figure-6

- SpO₂ of 95% and low-grade fever indicate clinically stable condition without severe respiratory involvement.

Conclusion:

Lung ultrasound in this 35-week pregnant patient with laboratory-confirmed COVID-19 revealed multiple B-lines and irregular pleural lines across several zones, indicative of interstitial changes. While third-trimester pregnancy is associated with physiological lung changes, the pleural line is not part of normal B-line physiology; therefore, these findings should be considered pathological. Overall, LUS provided reliable evidence of COVID-19–associated mild interstitial pneumonia in the context of pregnancy.

Table 6.

Lung ultrasound findings by zone in Patient N6

Zone	B-lines / thickened pleural line	Subpleural consolidation	Large consolidation / air bronchograms
R1	–	–	–
R2	–	–	–
R3	–	–	–
R4	+	–	–
R5	+	+	–
R6	+	+	–
L1	–	–	–
L2	–	–	–
L3	–	–	–
L4	–	–	–
L5	+	–	–
L6	+	+	–
Total Score	11 points	–	–

Patient N7: Male, 53 years old (Figure-7). Admitted on 18/03 with right-sided pneumonia. Radiographically, there was a perihilar infiltration on the right side. Lung ultrasound performed on 21/03 revealed consolidation in the right lower anterior region (R2 point).

LUS capabilities in bacterial pneumonia:

- Lung ultrasound successfully identified localized consolidation, strongly suggesting bacterial etiology.
- Unlike COVID-19, where interstitial involvement and B-lines dominate across multiple zones, in this case the pathology is localized and consolidative.

• LUS can not only confirm the presence of pneumonia but also help differentiate between viral and bacterial types based on localization, type of consolidation, and pleural line changes.

Conclusion:

Patient N7 represents a classic example of non-viral pneumonia, in which lung ultrasound effectively

confirmed localized consolidation consistent with radiographic findings. This case demonstrates that LUS is not limited to COVID-19 detection, but serves as a reliable method for diagnosing pulmonary pathologies, particularly when the involvement is localized and bacterial in nature.

Figure-7

Table-7

The table presents the laboratory, instrumental, and clinical data of several patients described above.

patiet	N1	N2	N3	N4	N5	N8	N9
date	5/03/21	12/03/21	10/03/21	24/04/21	17/03/21	7/05/21	6/05/21
Age/sex	61y/m	55y/f	62y/f	40y/f	63y/f	51y/m	45y/m
Ct score	12p	6/16p	4/9p	0/15	-	13p	17p
Lus-score	11/12p (5/03)	10p (13/03)	7-8p (13/03)	13p (8/05)	7-8p (17/03)	11p (8/05)	12p (8/05)
EF	56%	58%	56%	62%	60%	56%	60%
pasp	31mmhg	27mmhg	30mmhg	23mmhg	26mmhg	30mmhg	23mmhg
Chronic diseases	-	-	DM2, CABG	-	HTN	DM2	CKD crea-208
PCR	+	+	+	+	-	+	+
CRP	99mg/L	13mg/L	11mg/L	25mg/L	179mg/L	98mg/L	110mg/L
LDH	264U/L	282U/L	195U/L	197U/L	-	242U/L	318U/L
TROP	0,010µg/L	0,010µg/L	0,010µg/L	0,010µg/L	-	0,010µg/L	0,010µg/L
D.DIM	169(243) ng/ml	214(651) µg/L	328(651) µg/L	0,64 (0.5) mg/l	-	2,7 (0.5) mg/l	1150(651) µg/L
EOZ	0,4%	1,9%	0,7%	0.0	1.3%	0.3%	0.3%
NLR	4	3	7	11	5	5	6
SPO2 -AA	93%	92%	93%	90%	89%	92%	91%
T	38,0C	38,50C	37,40C	38,50C	37,50C	37,8oC	36,8oC

The patients presented in the table were treated in a general medical ward, with patient N2 later transferred to the intensive care unit. As the data indicate, the ultrasound (LUS) scores ranged from 5 to 15, corresponding to moderate severity according to the CLUE protocol. For patients with moderate pulmonary involvement who are oxygen-dependent, the protocol recommends continuing treatment in the general medical ward, while also considering the potential need for intensive care.

In summary, lung ultrasound in the medical ward represents a highly sensitive, versatile, and safe diagnostic tool with several advantages:

- It effectively detects typical COVID-19 findings, including multiple B-lines, consolidations, and pleural changes.
- It informs clinical decision-making even in the absence of laboratory or radiological confirmation.

- It facilitates rapid decision-making in high-risk groups (e.g., pregnant patients) [25] without ionizing radiation.

- It demonstrates high specificity in distinguishing non-viral, bacterial pneumonia from COVID-19.

In conclusion, the advantages and potential applications of lung ultrasound can be summarized as follows: it is non-invasive, rapid, and repeatable; it allows visual assessment of pathological processes, including in pregnant patients, for both COVID-19 and other pleuro-pulmonary conditions. During the COVID-19 pandemic, lung ultrasound has proven to be a valuable adjunct at various stages: for triage in emergency departments, monitoring patients in internal medicine wards, and in intensive or critical care units for risk stratification, complication prediction, and treatment efficacy monitoring. Additionally, lung ultrasound can

be applied in clinical research across multiple contexts and settings.

References

- Volpicelli G, Elbarbary M, Blaivas M, et al. International evidence-based recommendations for point-of-care lung ultrasound. *Intensive Care Med.* 2012;38:577–591. doi:10.1007/s00134-012-2513-4. PMID: 22392020.
- Lichtenstein DA. Lung ultrasound in the critically ill. *Ann Intensive Care.* 2014;4:1. doi:10.1186/2110-5820-4-1. PMID: 24359555.
- Lichtenstein D. *Whole body ultrasonography in the critically ill.* Springer; 2010.
- Soldati G, Smargiassi A, Inchingolo R, et al. Proposal for international standardization of the use of lung ultrasound for COVID-19 patients. *J Ultrasound Med.* 2020;39:1413–1419. doi:10.1002/jum.15285. PMID: 32298150.
- Poggiali E, Dacrema A, Bastoni D, et al. Can lung US help critical care clinicians in the early diagnosis of novel coronavirus (COVID-19) pneumonia? *Radiology.* 2020;296:E6–E6. doi:10.1148/radiol.2020200957. PMID: 32169637.
- Yasukawa K, Minami T. Point-of-care lung ultrasound findings in patients with novel coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pneumonia. *Am J Trop Med Hyg.* 2020;102:1198–1202. doi:10.4269/ajtmh.20-0289. PMID: 32329401.
- Lichtenstein DA. BLUE-protocol and FALLS-protocol. *Chest.* 2015;147:1659–1670. doi:10.1378/chest.14-2882. PMID: 25783875.
- Smith MJ, Hayward SA, Innes SM, Miller ASC. Point-of-care lung ultrasound in patients with COVID-19—a narrative review. *Anaesthesia.* 2020;75:1096–1104. doi:10.1111/anae.15082. PMID: 32405501.
- Volpicelli G, Caramello V, Cardinale L, et al. Lung ultrasound in emergency and critically ill patients: number of studies and accuracy. *Chest.* 2012;141:1177–1183. doi:10.1378/chest.11-2401. PMID: 22539348.
- Lichtenstein DA, Meziere GA. Relevance of lung ultrasound in the diagnosis of acute respiratory failure: the BLUE protocol. *Chest.* 2008;134:117–125. doi:10.1378/chest.07-2800. PMID: 18574271.
- Nouvenne A, Zani MD, Milanese G, et al. Lung ultrasound in COVID-19 pneumonia: correlations with chest CT on hospital admission. *Respir Med.* 2020;165:105954. doi:10.1016/j.rmed.2020.105954. PMID: 32607606.
- Buonsenso D, Pata D, Chiaretti A. Point-of-care lung ultrasound findings in novel coronavirus disease-19 pneumonia: a prospective study. *J Ultrasound Med.* 2020;39:1877–1884. doi:10.1002/jum.15284. PMID: 32421440.
- Huang Y, Wang S, Liu Y, et al. A preliminary study on the ultrasonic manifestations of peripulmonary lesions of non-critical novel coronavirus pneumonia (COVID-19). *SSRN Electron J.* 2020. doi:10.2139/ssrn.3544750.
- Reissig A, Copetti R, Kroegel C. Lung ultrasound in community-acquired pneumonia and in interstitial lung diseases. *Respiration.* 2014;87:179–189. doi:10.1159/000357980. PMID: 24240549.
- Volpicelli G, Elbarbary M, Blaivas M, et al. International evidence-based recommendations for point-of-care lung ultrasound. *Intensive Care Med.* 2012;38:577–591. doi:10.1007/s00134-012-2513-4.
- Lichtenstein DA. *Whole body ultrasonography in the critically ill.* Springer; 2010.
- Volpicelli G, Gargani L. Sonographic signs and patterns of COVID-19 pneumonia. *Ultrasound J.* 2020;12:22. doi:10.1186/s13089-020-00171-w.
- Soldati G, Smargiassi A, Inchingolo R, et al. Lung ultrasonography for patients with COVID-19: a narrative review. *Ultrasound Med Biol.* 2020;46:1291–1300. doi:10.1016/j.ultrasmedbio.2020.04.021.
- Manivel V, Lesnewski A, Shamim S, Carbonatto G, Govindan T. CLUE: COVID-19 lung ultrasound in emergency department. *Emerg Med Australas.* 2020;32:1–6. doi:10.1111/1742-6723.13546.
- Lichtenstein DA. *Whole Body Ultrasonography in the Critically Ill.* Springer; 2010. Chapter 14.
- Peng QY, Wang XT, Zhang LN. Findings of lung ultrasonography of novel coronavirus pneumonia during the 2019–2020 epidemic. *Intensive Care Med.* 2020;46:849–850. doi:10.1007/s00134-020-05985-9. PMID: 32199621.
- Dargent A, Chatelain E, Si-Mohamed S, Simon M, Baudry T, Kreitmann L, Quenot JP, Cour M, Argaud L; the COVIDLUS study group. Lung ultrasound score as a tool to monitor disease progression and detect ventilator-associated pneumonia during COVID-19-associated ARDS. *Intensive Care Med.* 2021;47:849–860. doi:10.1007/s00134-021-06407-1. PMID: 34107394.
- Vetrugno L, Baciarello M, Bignami E, Bonetti A, Saturno F, Orso D, et al. Lung ultrasound signs and their correlation with clinical symptoms in COVID-19 pregnant women: the “PINK CO” observational study. *Front Med.* 2022;8:768261. doi:10.3389/fmed.2021.768261.